

ECONOMETRIC MODELING OF INTEREST COSTS OF COMMERCIAL BANKS

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ANNOTATION: In this article, the interaction of deposit operations offered to the population in all commercial banks in the Republic of Uzbekistan on the bank's financial condition is analyzed in econometric models.

KEY WORDS: commercial banks, deposit operations, savings deposit, demand deposits, term deposits, net profit, interest expense, logarithmic model, econometric modeling, Brosch Pogan test, Log likelihood, Akaike, Bayeseian.

INTRODUCTION

One of the main areas of improvement of financial control is the application of international standards of accounting and auditing to this process. As a result of categorization of accounts that take into account the costs of settlement operations shown to customers in banks, sources of financing, types of activities, directions, places of occurrence of costs, their items are adapted to the requirements of national and international standards of accounting and control.

If we study and analyze the period from the origin of banks to the present day, we can see that the concepts of savings and deposits appeared as soon as the first banks appeared. Because the rich and the poor have always existed and formed. We would not be wrong if we say that the demand of money holders to put their excess funds in a safe place created the basis for the emergence of the concept of deposit.

It is known that the banking system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the change of money circulation and economic growth in the country directly depends on the activity of commercial banks in this region. That is, as the activity of commercial banks expands and efficiency indicators increase, the banking system of the country,

the correct distribution of money aggregates, the control of the money supply, and at the same time the economic growth also increases. In particular, if we see the development of the banking system operating in our country in the segment of commercial banks, we can assess the extent to which the economic indicators of the banks have been established.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

First of all, the accounting daily balance for the last date is required, and the daily balance is fully analyzed as necessary. After that, compatibility of synthetic (cumulative) and analytical (spread) calculations is checked one by one by comparing them. In addition, the section describes the procedure for opening accounts and sub-accounts for customers, the correct formalization and completeness of their legal documents, the timely and correct registration and recording of opened and closed accounts in the 61-form book. complete and legal conclusion of service contracts with customers, correct and complete establishment, calculation and collection of service fees for services rendered from customers, formalization and acceptance of daily documents and its transfer, the establishment of the final control in the department is seen based on the relevant guidelines.

Verification of settlement transactions provided to customers in banks in the Republic of Uzbekistan is based on the instructions of the Central Bank № 1831, 1948, 3229 and the "Accounting Plan of Accounts in Commercial Banks of the Republic of Uzbekistan", additions and changes to them and other regulatory documents of the Central Bank.

The audit begins with seeing how well things are done in the accounting department. The existence of the work plan and work structure of the department, the correct distribution of tasks among the employees, their provision with the necessary manuals, and the degree to which the employees know the manuals related to their work are studied. During the audit period, analytical account balances and

synthetic account balances are compared on all balance accounts on one of the days determined by the head of the audit.

The research relied on such methods of scientific knowledge as dialectic, logic, analysis and synthesis, complex approach.

RESULTS

The comparison of the analytical account with the synthetic account of the internal accounts of the bank, where the equipment sheets and books are the basis for the analytical account, is carried out by calculating the open amounts in the books with the amounts indicated in these sheets. Transaction books or synthetic personal accounts are counted as each open amount written to the account on the balance sheet account, and the end is remembered by the balance issued on this account and on the balance sheet.

The legality of giving and transferring funds from open-ended deposit accounts, loans and other accounts, which are not provided for in other sections of the audit of operations, can be checked on documents and personal accounts to the extent determined by the head of the audit. In this case, it is necessary to pay special attention to the orders for the purchase of material goods, especially the operations signed by officials who do not provide services to this client, and at the same time to check whether the documents are correctly executed.

Soffoyda	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
jamgama	-.8726428	.6534433	-1.34	0.189	-2.189571	.4442856
talabqo	-.0875734	.2802514	-0.31	0.756	-.652383	.4772361
muddatli	.5341338	.2263257	2.36	0.023	.0780043	.9902632
_cons	4561.951	3066.379	1.49	0.144	-1617.929	10741.83

Figure 1. Analysis of the relationship between deposits and net profit of commercial banks

$$Y = -0.87x_1 - 0.08x_2 + 0.53x_3 + 4561.95$$

In this

Y = net profit

x_1= savings deposit

x_2= deposit funds until demand

x_3= term deposits

Our regression analysis shows that the total deposit operations of commercial banks are a passive operation of the banking system, i.e. bank liabilities, which indirectly affect the bank's profit. It can be seen that, based on the results of the analysis, we found out that the total term deposits of commercial banks have an indirect effect on the increase in bank profits.

Modeling the relationship between the net profit of commercial banks and total types of deposits

	1-model	2-model	3-model	4-model
Net profit	*			*
Time deposits	0.24		0.00005	
ln net profit		*	*	
ln time deposits		0.88		3725.27
F-test	41.16	24.46	24.58	35.12
R^2	0.47	0.35	0.35	0.43
Adj R^2	0.46	0.33	0.33	0.42
Root MSE	2104.2	0.62	0.62	2181.1
Brosch	5.0	0.41	1.01	7.22
Pogan test	Prob>chi2_ 0.02	Prob>chi2_ 0.52	Prob>chi2_ 0.31	Prob>chi2_ 0.0072
Durbin Watson test	0.69	0.80	0.81	0.64

If we analyze our models of 4 different methods presented in the table above, the most reliable is the 2nd model, that is, the logarithmic model, according to which, if the balance of fixed deposits of commercial banks increases by 1%, the net profit of commercial banks increases by 0.88% indirectly leads to an increase.

Continuing this research, we will consider the relationship between the deposit operations offered to the population in commercial banks and the total interest costs of commercial banks in one of the econometric models.

Table 2.

Analysis of interest costs of commercial banks in ARIMA tests

Mezonlar	A ARIMA(2,1,0)	B ARIMA(2,1,1)	C ARIMA(2,1,2)	D ARIMA(1,1,0)	E ARIMA(1,1,1)	O p t i m a l
Parametrlar	3/0	3/0	3/0	3/0	3/0	
Sigma	0.66	0.61	-0.32	0.68	0.67	C
Log likelihood	-46.74	-43.91	-46.20	-47.84	-47.02	B
Akaike	103.49	97.82	106.40	103.67	104.05	B
Bayeseian	112.63	106.96	119.20	110.99	113.19	B

Through this econometric analysis, we have tested various tests to reduce the interest costs of commercial banks to the ARIMA model. In particular, as a result of conducting log likelihood, Akaike and Bayesian tests, we accepted option B as it fully meets all standards from options A, B, C, D and E.

DISCUSSION

The auditor verifies that the application is submitted with the register, that the first copy of the register is signed by the head and chief accountant of the enterprise, that there is a stamp, and that the above indicators are accurate. The accepted application is written in three copies if the service is provided in one bank. The first

and second copies remain in the bank pending payment. The bank gives the third copy of the application to the Payer for acceptance, not later than the next working day, indicating the date of receipt of the document. The auditor checks that a copy of the application is attached to the bank's daily collection of documents, and the extract from the recipient's personal account.

Based on the results of our analysis, we found out that savings deposits are the main indicator of the increase in the interest cost of commercial banks, and the lowest indicator is term deposit operations, i.e. 26%. we can see that it affects the increase in costs.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, it should be said that one of the main directions of improving financial control in banks is the application of international standards of accounting and state auditing to this process, the classification of accounts that take into account the costs of bank book operations, sources of financing, types of activities, directions , the places where costs occur, the process of mutual adaptation of national and international standards takes place. In this regard, it is proposed to apply international accounting standards in banks in a comprehensive manner, to implement a series of accounts that take into account the costs of settlement operations of commercial banks.

Based on the results of our general analysis, we can conclude that an increase in the volume of term deposit operations in commercial banks can indirectly have a positive effect on the bank's profit and lead to a decrease in interest expenses.

List of used literature

1. "On requirements for internal audit of commercial banks" № 3302
REGULATION 2021 April 16
2. On the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan (new edition) November 11, 2019
3. On banks and banking activities (new version) November 5, 2019

4. Umarov Z. A., Muminova P. I. TIJORAT BANKLARIDA DEPOZIT OPERATSIYALARI AUDITINING NAZARIY ASOSLARI HAMDA YURITILISH TARTIBI //INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – С. 50-54.

5. Мўминов, З. Ш. ў., Муминова П. И. қ., & Мехмонов, С. (2022). БЮДЖЕТ ТАШКИЛОТЛАРИДА ХАРАЖАТЛАР ҲИСОБИ ВА ИЧКИ НАЗОРАТИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 1(1), 40–46.

6. Muminova, P. I., & Umarov, Z. A. (2022). BANKLARDA MIJOZLARGA KO‘RSATILADIGAN HISOB-KITOB OPERATSIYALARI AUDITI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 1(1), 113–124.

7. P.I. Sayitkulova, A.Z. Avlokulov. The International Audit Standards and Composition of the AUDIT, as well as the Importance of Tax Accounting. Материалы конференции, Международные стандарты учета и аудита: практика применения в условиях цифровой экономики 26-29, (2020).

8. www.gov.uz - the portal of the State Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

9. www.press-service.uz - the official website of the Press Service of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

10. www.cbu.uz is the official website of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

11. www.cer.uz - the official website of the Economic Research Center.